

RURAL MARKETING IN TAMIL NADU – A STUDY OF STRATEGIES, OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

Dr. C S SENTHILKUMAR, Associate Professor, PG and Research Department of Commerce IB,
Hindusthan College of Arts & Science Coimbatore.

&

S. PRANAVKUMAR, II M.COM IB Student, PG and Research Department of Commerce IB,
Hindusthan College of Arts & Science Coimbatore.

ABSTRACT

Background: Rural marketing involves the process of developing, pricing, promoting, and assessing products to facilitate the exchange between rural and urban markets, aiming to satisfy consumer needs. Due to the intense competition in urban markets, many companies are now focusing on expanding their products to rural areas. In recent years, the rural market has seen substantial growth, significantly boosting the purchasing power of rural communities. This growth can be partly attributed to the Green Revolution in Tamil Nadu, which has increased the consumption of manufactured goods in these areas. The market dynamics in rural regions are evolving rapidly, with rural families having their own aspirations and a willingness to pay a fair price for quality products. Ignoring the potential of rural markets is no longer an option for companies, despite the various challenges they face in these areas.

Aim: To review the literature related to rural marketing in Tamil Nadu.

Objectives: This study aims to examine several key aspects of rural marketing in Tamil Nadu

- Nature and characteristics
- Strategies adopted
- Opportunities and challenges

Discussion: For a company to successfully penetrate the rural market, it must first conduct a thorough evaluation of the target rural market. This involves understanding specific characteristics of the rural market and employing various marketing strategies tailored to different situations.

Keywords: Rural Marketing, Strategies, Purchasing Power, Opportunities, Challenge.

INTRODUCTION

Rural marketing in Tamil Nadu has become an essential focus for companies looking to expand their reach beyond urban markets. With increasing competition in urban areas, businesses are now turning their attention to the vast, untapped potential of rural markets. This essay explores the various strategies employed by companies, the opportunities that rural markets present, and the challenges they face in these regions.

The Nature and Characteristics of Rural Markets in Tamil Nadu

The rural market in Tamil Nadu is characterized by unique socio-economic dynamics that differ significantly from urban areas. Rural consumers have distinct needs, preferences, and purchasing behaviors. The increasing influence of the Green Revolution has resulted in higher disposable incomes and greater purchasing power among rural communities. This demographic shift has led to a surge in demand for manufactured products, including consumer goods, electronics, and agricultural equipment.

Rural areas in Tamil Nadu are also marked by close-knit communities with strong cultural ties. Marketing strategies that resonate with these cultural values are more likely to succeed. Additionally, the rural market is not homogenous; it consists of various segments with differing economic statuses and consumption patterns. Understanding these nuances is crucial for any company aiming to capture this market.

Strategies for Rural Marketing

To effectively market products in rural Tamil Nadu, companies need to adopt tailored strategies that address the unique characteristics of the rural consumer base. Key strategies include:

1. **Localized Marketing:** Customizing marketing campaigns to reflect local culture, language, and traditions helps in building a connection with rural consumers. Companies often use local festivals and events to promote their products.
2. **Affordable Pricing:** Offering products at competitive prices is crucial in rural markets where consumers are price-sensitive. Introducing smaller, affordable packaging can make products more accessible.

3. **Distribution Networks:** Establishing an efficient distribution network is essential for reaching remote areas. This can include partnering with local retailers and using decentralized distribution models to ensure product availability.
4. **Education and Awareness:** Educating rural consumers about the benefits and usage of products through demonstrations and community outreach programs can drive adoption. Companies often use mobile vans and local influencers to disseminate information.
5. **Technology Utilization:** Leveraging technology such as mobile marketing and digital platforms can enhance reach and engagement. Many rural consumers are now accessing information and services via smart phones, making digital marketing an effective tool.

Opportunities in Rural Marketing

The rural market in Tamil Nadu presents numerous opportunities for companies willing to invest in understanding and catering to this segment. Some of the notable opportunities include:

1. **Untapped Potential:** With a large portion of the population residing in rural areas, there is a significant market potential that remains largely untapped.
2. **Growing Purchasing Power:** Increased agricultural productivity and government initiatives have led to a rise in disposable incomes in rural areas, translating into higher demand for a variety of products.
3. **Infrastructure Development:** Improved infrastructure, including better roads and enhanced connectivity, facilitates easier access to rural markets, reducing logistical challenges.
4. **Government Support:** Various government schemes aimed at rural development provide a conducive environment for businesses to expand their operations in these areas.
5. **Diversification:** The rural market offers opportunities for companies to diversify their product lines to cater to different needs, from basic necessities to luxury items.

Challenges in Rural Marketing

Despite the numerous opportunities, companies face several challenges in rural marketing:

1. **Infrastructure Constraints:** Inadequate infrastructure in some areas, such as poor road conditions and lack of reliable electricity, can hinder effective distribution and marketing efforts.

2. **Consumer Awareness:** Low levels of literacy and limited exposure to modern marketing can make it difficult to communicate product benefits to rural consumers.
3. **Cultural Barriers:** Deep-rooted cultural practices and resistance to change can pose challenges in introducing new products and services.
4. **Logistical Issues:** Ensuring consistent product availability and managing supply chains in remote areas can be complex and costly.
5. **Competition from Local Brands:** Local brands that are well-entrenched in rural markets can pose stiff competition to new entrants.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The processing of fruits and vegetables is largely controlled by unorganized players, who hold a 70% share of the total market. In recent years, the industry has experienced significant growth in the Ready to eat foods sector, including frozen vegetables and processed mushrooms. A major challenge for this sector is the lack of adequate infrastructure to store produce. Additionally, there is a strong cultural preference for fresh fruits and vegetables over processed ones (Mohammed Rais, 2013).

According to a report, the global demand for fruit and vegetable processing was valued at USD 203.3 billion in 2014 and is projected to reach USD 319.9 billion by 2020, with an anticipated CAGR of 7.9% from 2016 to 2020. This study examines the drivers and restraints affecting demand in the fruit and vegetable processing market and explores the opportunities available at a global level (Global Fruit and Vegetable Market Research Report, 2014).

The Food Processing Industry benefits both farmers and processors, offering significant potential in India despite the current small size of the industry.

Table 1 highlights the processing levels of various food products in India:

Food Products Segment	Processing Level in India
Fruits and Vegetables	2.2%
Fisheries	26%
Poultry	6%
Buffalo Meat	20%
Milk	35%

Source: Ministry of Food Processing Industry, Govt. of India

There is considerable potential for organized processing players in the fruits and vegetables sector due to the currently low levels of processing and the vast supply base. Additionally, there is substantial international demand for both fresh and processed fruits and vegetables (Pradip Kumar Biswas, Performance of Indian Food Products Industry, CSIR – National Institute of Science Technology and Development Studies, 2015).

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

Objectives of the Study

- To find out demographic, economic pattern, occupation pattern of the Tamil Nadu.
- To assess the method of strategies, opportunities and challenges.
- To find out the gain knowledge about rural marketing in Tamil Nadu.
- To valuable suggestion about rural marketing in Tamil Nadu.

Research design: The analyst followed enlightening test plan for the investigation.

Universe of the study: The universe of the current assessment is the rural marketing in Tamil Nadu.

Tools for data collection: The study based on primary and secondary data. The primary and secondary data had collected from data base on rural marketing in Tamil Nadu.

DEMOGRAPHY OF TAMIL NADU

Introduction

Tamil Nadu, the 11th largest state in India by area, is the seventh most populous, with Tamil as its main language, dating back to 500 BC. The state's capital, Chennai, is located on the eastern coastline of India. Tamil Nadu is renowned for its ancient temples and monuments, many of which are UNESCO World Heritage sites. Despite its rich historical significance, Tamil Nadu is also a rapidly developing center for technology and trade.

Population and Demographics

According to the 2011 census, Tamil Nadu's population stands at approximately 72 million, reflecting significant growth from the 62 million recorded in the 2001 census. The state's population density is 555 people per square kilometer, exceeding the national average by about 150 points. With a growth rate of around 15%, the population is expected to continue rising due to improvements in infrastructure and development. The literacy rate in Tamil Nadu is about 80%, significantly higher than the national average, demonstrating the state's commitment to education. The sex ratio is also favorable at 996 females for every 1,000 males, above the national average of 940.

Population Statistics (2011 Census)

- **Total Population:** 72,147,030 (Male: 36,137,975; Female: 36,009,055)
- **Population Growth Rate:** 15.61%
- **Percentage of National Population:** 5.96%
- **Sex Ratio:** 996 females per 1,000 males
- **Density:** 555 per km²
- **Literacy Rate:** 80.09% (Male: 86.77%, Female: 73.14%)

Income Generation in Rural Areas

Income generation in rural Tamil Nadu is predominantly related to agriculture, with 75% of total income derived from agricultural activities. The table below illustrates the distribution of income sources in rural areas:

Source of Income	Percentage
Agriculture	58.8%
Agricultural Wages	16.1%
Business and Crafts	8.8%
Non-agricultural Wages	7.2%
Salaries	2.5%
Current Transfers	1.9%
Others	4.7%

The dominance of agriculture as the primary occupation means that growth in this sector directly contributes to rural prosperity, offering significant potential for marketers. Marketers must tailor their strategies to target specific segments within the rural population, including small farmers, marginal landholders, and wealthy landowners.

Occupation Patterns in Rural Areas

The primary occupation for the majority of the rural population in Tamil Nadu is agriculture and related activities. The occupation pattern is detailed below:

Occupation	Percentage
Agriculture	50%
Agricultural Labour	27%
Business	10%
Non-agricultural Labour	9%
Salary Earners	2%
Non-gainfully Employed	2%

Approximately 77% of the rural population relies solely on land-based activities for their livelihood. This dependency means that rural income and disposable income are heavily influenced by agricultural conditions, such as rainfall, weather, and the availability of appropriate technology. Favorable conditions lead to prosperity, as seen in states like Punjab, Haryana, and Western Uttar Pradesh, while adverse conditions can significantly reduce rural income.

SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Develop common facilities for loading and unloading, drying, cleaning, washing, ripening, and packing in an organized manner.
2. Regularly provide supportive functions such as waste management, parking facilities, and sufficient market space for loading and unloading commodities.
3. Ensure the provision and awareness of functional infrastructure for assembling, grading, weighing, quality certification, waxing, standardizing, and other value-added processes.
4. Provide education and infrastructure for direct marketing, e-trading, e-buying, and mobile delivery of commodities.
5. According to Porter's arguments, the value chain should be a source of competitive advantage and simultaneously add value to customers.
6. Implement effective waste management practices. Given the high biodegradability of commodities, waste can be transported and used as manure.
7. Identify reliable farmers and establish direct ties between wholesalers, retailers, and farmers. Ensure that produce is tested in labs to meet WHO-prescribed safety standards before marketing to ensure quality and reliability.
8. Introduce transparency in the market to prevent black marketing and hoarding, and to regulate product prices.
9. Utilize Madurai's air connectivity to facilitate international cargo lifting, increasing business volume, quality, and proceeds.
10. Facilitate plant quarantine for agricultural products in Madurai to ensure food safety and security standards. Organize packing and allied activities to support and grow the industry.

CONCLUSION

Tamil Nadu presents a unique blend of historical significance and rapid modern development. With a growing population, high literacy rates, and a strong reliance on agriculture, the state offers significant opportunities for growth and investment, particularly in the rural sector. Understanding

the demographic and economic landscape is crucial for leveraging these opportunities and driving further development in Tamil Nadu. Rural marketing in Tamil Nadu offers a promising avenue for business expansion, provided companies are willing to navigate its unique landscape with well-thought-out strategies. By understanding the distinct characteristics of rural consumers, leveraging opportunities, and addressing the inherent challenges, businesses can unlock significant growth potential. The key lies in adopting a localized approach, fostering community engagement, and continuously adapting to the evolving rural market dynamics. As rural areas continue to develop, the future of rural marketing in Tamil Nadu looks bright, offering a win-win scenario for both consumers and companies.

REFERENCES

- Ashfaque Ahmed, Rural Marketing Strategies for Selling Products & Services: Issues & Challenges, Journal of Business Management & Social Sciences Research, Volume 2, No.1, January 2013.
- Asian J. Management; 6(4): Oct-Dec 2015, page 336-341. Avdesh, K. S., & Satyaprakash, P, Rural Marketing: India Perspective (1st ed.). New Age International Pvt. Ltd, 2005.
- Avinash Kumar, “Rural Marketing Strategies, Issues and Challenges.”, The International journal of analytical and experimental modal analysis, volume XI, issue XII, December 2019, page number: 2769 – 2781.
- Bhavika Pandita Hakhroo, Review of Rural Marketing in India and Innovations in Rural Marketing, International Journal of Engineering and Management Research, Volume-10, Issue- 5, October 2020.
- Deepak Bhandari, Gaurav Khanna, Research Article on Rural Marketing - A Study in Jodhpur District, international journal for innovative research in multidisciplinary field, Volume - 2, Issue - 7, July – 2016.
- Gopala Swamy T P, Rural Marketing, Second Edition, Excel Books, 2003. Gurukul Business Review (GBR) Vol. 7, 2011, pp. 125-130

- Hagargi, A. K. S., Rural Market in India: Some Opportunities and Challenges. International Journal of Exclusive Management Research, 2011, 1(1). Journal: Rural Marketing: The Wall Street Journal, Business Insight column, June 15, 2012
- Kashyap. P and Ruat. S, The Rural Marketing Book – Text & Practice, 2007.
- Kavitha, T. C., A Comparative Study of Growth, Challenges and Opportunities in FMCG of Rural Market. Inter science Management Review, 2012, 2(3).
- Kumar, P. & Dangi, N., Rural marketing in India: Challenges and opportunities. International Journal of Management and Social Sciences Research (IJMSSR), 2013, Aug, 2(8), 93-100.
- Kotlar, P., Marketing for Non-Profit organization. Prentice Hall of India, New Delhi Management, 2010.
- Kotni, VV D.P, Prospect and problems of Indian rural markets. ZENITH International Journal of Business Economics and Management Research, 2012, 2(3), 200-213
- Kumar A., Hagagi, S, Rural market in India: some opportunities and challenges. International Journal of Exclusive Management Research, 2011, 1(1), 1-15.
- Mannappa, O, Rural marketing challenges in the new millennium. Delhi Business Review, 2003, 4(1). Marketing to rural India: A Changing Paradigm by Deepti Srivastava, APJRBM Volume 1, Issue 3, December 2010.
- Menon, N. & K, S., Customization of marketing mix for rural markets. Marketing to Rural Consumers IIM-. Kozhikode, 2008, pp. 175-182.
- Naina Sharma, Rising Horizons of Rural Marketing in India, JAC: A Journal of Composition Theory, Volume XIII, Issue VI, June 2020, page: 29 – 39.